

Research Questionnaire

Dear Respondent,

You are invited to participate in a research study that aims to examine how corporate social responsibility (CSR) and hotel reputation influence customer loyalty in star-rated hotels. Your insights are valuable in contributing to academic research in the hospitality industry.

This questionnaire will take approximately 5–7 minutes to complete. Your responses will remain strictly confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes. Participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Thank you for your time and support.

Sincerely,

Dr. Ajit Singh

Ethical Disclaimer

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Formal ethical approval was not sought as the research involved voluntary participation by adults (aged 18 years and above) in a non-invasive, anonymous survey. All efforts were made to ensure the rights, privacy, and confidentiality of participants were fully protected throughout the study.

Consent

I have read the information above and voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Instructions

Please indicate your level of agreement by ticking one of the boxes:

1 = Strongly Disagree | 2 = Disagree | 3 = Neutral | 4 = Agree | 5 = Strongly Agree

Section B: Corporate Social Responsibility

Statement

The hotel you last visited checks the quality of goods and/or services provided to customers. **1 2 3 4 5**

The hotel you last visited is helpful to customers and advises them about its products/services. **1 2 3 4 5**

The hotel you last visited respects its commitments to customers. **1 2 3 4 5**

Statement

- The hotel you last visited invests in innovations that are to the advantage of customers. 1 2 3 4 5
- The hotel you last visited ensures its products/services are accessible for all customers. 1 2 3 4 5
- The hotel you last visited seems to be environmentally responsible. 1 2 3 4 5
- The hotel you last visited looks like a good company to work for. 1 2 3 4 5
- The hotel you last visited seems to treat its people well. 1 2 3 4 5

Section C: Hotel Reputation

Statement

- From my experience in the lodging, this hotel is well managed. 1 2 3 4 5
- From my experience in the lodging, this hotel has good employees. 1 2 3 4 5
- From my experience in the lodging, this hotel is customer focused. 1 2 3 4 5

Section D: Customer Loyalty

Statement

- I would encourage friends and relatives to stay/visit the hotel. 1 2 3 4 5
- I would stay/visit the hotel in the future. 1 2 3 4 5
- I would say positive things about the hotel to others. 1 2 3 4 5
- I consider the hotel to be my first choice to stay in this city. 1 2 3 4 5
- Whenever I get the chance, I would continue to stay at the hotel. 1 2 3 4 5

Any additional comments or suggestions related to your hotel experience:
